

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND PERSONAL COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The purpose of the article is the theoretical substantiation and experimental approbation of pedagogical conditions that ensure effective management of the process of professional and personal competencies of students in international universities.*

Keywords: *methodology, development, professional qualities, personal competence, students.*

In international experience, the main characteristics of the educational process in a modern vocational school are multifunctionality, multilevelness, innovation, intensity, which determine the structure and content of professional training, determine the requirements for methodological and technological support. In these conditions of modernization of the vocational education system in accordance with modern demands and socio-cultural requirements, the task of effective management of professional and personal development of students is of particular relevance. The successful solution of this task is directly related to improving the quality of education, the effectiveness of the implementation of the competence-based approach in the personnel training system.

In our republic, a number of works have been carried out in higher educational institutions to introduce technologies for managing students' professional and personal competencies and improve their improvement, which are the product of scientific and technical achievements in the education system.

The theoretical and methodological foundations of the use of modern didactic programs as a tool for improving the professional competence of students in our republic have been studied by scientists R.X. Juraev, A.R. Khodzhaboev, N.A. Muslimov, Sh.S. Sharipov, K.T. Olimov, M.B.Urazova, R.G.Isyanov, N.N. Azizkhodzhayeva, Z.K.Ismailova, D.O.Himmataliev, J.A.Khamidov, O.A.Kuisinov, R.K.Choriev, B.A.Nazarova and others.

Among the main trends gaining strength as a result of this phenomenon and provoking new phenomena in the higher education system, UNESCO notes the increasing role of the knowledge economy and market relations, the emergence of new international agreements on trade in educational services, and innovations in information and communication technologies.

The purpose of educational work at the lyceum is to create conditions for the full development of the upbringing of a moral, responsible, proactive and competent citizen of Uzbekistan, capable of constant personal and professional self-improvement.

The tasks of educational work are arranged in the following sequence:

- formation of a unified educational space of the lyceum through the integration of basic and additional education;
- improving the system of educational work in teams;

- to continue the formation of the basic national values through the introduction of a program of education, development and socialization of the personality of students;
- preserving and strengthening the health of students, instilling in them the skills of a healthy lifestyle, for the prevention of offenses and crimes by minors;
- creation of conditions for the manifestation and motivation of creative activity of pupils in various fields of socially significant activity;
- development of the system of continuing education; continuity of levels and stages of education;
- support for research and project activities;
- mastering and using in practice new pedagogical technologies and methods of educational work;
- development of various forms of student self-government.

The high effectiveness of the influence of the educational environment on the process of formation of the humanistic orientation of the personality of a Russian student in modern society is determined by the following conditions:

- educational potential, i.e., value orientations in the professional sphere, the idea of the profession and social attitudes towards mastering it, professional competence, intelligence, the ability to self-education and psychological literacy;
- creative potential, that is, initiative, creativity, social activity, perseverance, dedication and organizational qualities;
- communicative potential, that is, openness, delicacy, kindness, tolerance, a sense of tact, empathy, intuition, the ability to empathize, decency and willingness to cooperate;
- moral potential, that is, honesty, responsibility, regulation of one's behavior, understanding of one's capabilities, spiritual and general culture, citizenship and patriotism.

Managing the process of adaptation of students throughout all years of study at the university creates the necessary organizational and substantive basis for the formation of the necessary level of readiness for solving the entire complex of professional tasks, ensures a high level of professional stability.

The educational environment of the university is a system of pedagogical conditions for the formation of a personality according to a given social pattern, as well as opportunities for its development, which are contained in the spatial, subject and social environment.

Vocational training in an educational institution is a complex, multifunctional, dialectically developing system, which is united by a target setting and includes methods, forms and types of both educational and extracurricular activities aimed at theoretical and practical training of students.

The model of the educational environment of an international institution focused on effective management of professional and personal development of students includes the following elements:

- a target block that takes into account the purpose of defining the specifics of the educational environment and research
- a substantial block, it describes the factors and resources for the development of professional and personal competencies of students, as well as pedagogical conditions that determine the development of professional competence of students through the activation of foreign cooperation;

- an activity block containing educational information, which is the basis for the formation of a system of personally significant knowledge, methodological forms of development of professional and personal competencies of students, forms of interaction - forms of distance learning, network communication of leaders, organization of a unified database of information resources, exchange of experience in international relations;

- a diagnostic block describing the criteria for evaluating the development of professional and personal competencies of students - motivational-personal, cognitive-creative, communicative-activity, as well as indicators for evaluating the development of personal and professional competencies of students - low, medium and high;

- an effective block that includes the result of all the experiments conducted as a result of forming a student with developed professional and personal competencies.

At the same time, the presented blocks ensure the multidimensionality of the educational environment, which includes subsystems characterized as a learning environment and an educational environment.

Regarding the process of educational and professional adaptation of students, we identify the following adaptive qualities:

- the presence of solid basic knowledge in general education and special subjects;
- the ability to independent cognitive activity;
- the presence of professional and personal qualities.

Let's highlight the following indicators of students' adaptability in the framework of managing their professional and personal competencies:

- satisfaction with the learning content, learning conditions, and interpersonal relationships in the group;

- orientation towards continuing studies;
- attending academic classes and actively participating in them;
- mastering the rational methods of educational activities;
- strict adherence to the regime of study, work and rest;
- working capacity;
- manifestation of the qualities of mental activity (independence, activity, criticality, etc.);

the level of assimilation of the system of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for continuing education at the university.

The educational and professional adaptation of students to the university educational process is a leading factor and resource for professional and personal development. The university educational environment serves as the basis for the implementation of personality-oriented educational technologies, allows you to create the necessary conditions for the formation of a humanistic personality orientation. Educational and professional adaptation is characterized by the success of students in educational and cognitive activities, the presence of value orientations, and developed communicative skills. In their entirety, these components are taken into account as fully as possible in the process of studying the professional and personal competencies of students in the educational environment of a modern university. In the process of studying at an educational institution, the formation of a personality occurs in the process of its socialization and self-development. It is socialization that introduces young people to socio-cultural and spiritual values, and self-development ensures constant personal growth in spiritual development, in the formation of creative individuality.

Figure 1. A model for the development of professional and personal competencies of students based on international experience

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– moral potential, that is, honesty, responsibility, regulation of one's behavior, understanding of one's capabilities, spiritual and general culture, citizenship and patriotism;

– qualification potential i.e. self-confidence, entrepreneurship, competitiveness, intellectual maturity (developed cognitive interests, the ability to find a constructive solution to a problem, critical thinking).

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